

THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF GAME METHODS IN ENGLISH TEACHING

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Abstract. This article talks about the use of various interesting game methods in teaching English. At the same time, information is given about the importance of the game method for the development of the mind of young people.

Keywords: "Pictionary", "Charades", "20 objects", "Letter Scramble", "questions and answers", memory exercise.

Аннотатсия. В данной статье рассказывается об использовании различных интересных игровых методов в обучении английскому языку. При этом даётся информация о значении игрового метода для развития мышления молодёжи.

Ключевые слова: «Иллюстрированный словарь», «Шарады», «20 предметов», «Битва букв», «Вопросы и ответы», упражнение на память.

Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ingliz tilini o'qitishda turli xil qiziqarli o'yinlardan foydalanish haqida so'z boradi. Shuning bilan birgalikda yoshlarning bilimlilik salmog'ini oshirishdagi o'yin metodining muhurligi haqida ham ma'lumotlar beriladi.

Kalit so'zlar: Pictionary", "Charades", "20 objects", "Letter Scramble", "savollar va javoblar", хотира mashqlari.

INTRODUCTION. In today's rapidly developing world, the demand for learning various fields, especially foreign languages, and the attention to developing the spiritual literacy of young people is increasing. At the same time, in order to further promote science and literacy among young people, new ways of teaching foreign languages easily and quickly are being developed. A vivid example of this is learning foreign languages by playing interesting games. In today's modern classrooms, we can see a number of new technologies, and this in turn makes it easier for young people to learn not only languages, but also mental arithmetic, mathematics, physics and other specific sciences. We know that various colorful and musical games, cartoons and such methods are very useful to increase the interest of young children in learning languages and other subjects. In order to activate passive students in the classroom through interesting team games and improve their spiritual literacy, teachers are now using various methods consisting of games.

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METHODS. As an example, we can include the "pictionary" drawing style. The procedure for this game is as follows: the teacher divides the students in the classroom into two groups and names them according to the group's wishes. The board should be a white magnetic board, a long dividing line is drawn on it, and one participant from each group is called. Each of them is shown one picture and students turn to the board and start drawing quickly. The first group to find the English name of this picture will be awarded 1 point. If the score of one of the groups is 10 points, this group is considered the winner and the teacher will give a kit or souvenir.

Another style is Charades. This method is very similar to pictionary, but in this game, instead of drawing, the participants explain through gestures. What is required from the group members is to find the name of this word in English. Also, the name of our next game is "20 objects". Through this game, students will effectively develop their memory and vocabulary. In this game, the teacher lists 20 objects in the classroom on the table and calls his students, begins to say the names of the objects one by one in English, which of the students can say these objects in English without breaking the sequence, that is the winner. the student is the winner. Our next game is Letter Scramble, in which the teacher pastes letters on the board in a mixed form and asks the students to find words in order to check the vocabulary that the students have recently learned. Questions and answers (questions and answers), that is, during the lesson, it

consists of asking students questions on the topic, discussing them, and finding answers.

RESULTS. The types of questions taught above are games that help students to strengthen their knowledge on the subject. In addition, one of the types of games that are very useful not only for children but also for adults is the game of asking for synonyms, that is, the game of asking for words with the same meaning. This game is usually very useful for students, because it is a very useful and effective way to know synonyms when they are reading English articles or doing different types of reading exercises. In addition, memory exercises played in English. It is not an exaggeration to say that this game is one of the methods that helps to memorize words quickly and qualitatively for students studying in preschool and elementary schools. This game is done through the following process, ten students are selected from the class and they start to repeat the words learned earlier in the lessons in Burmese English. In a sequential manner, students say their words without breaking the order of the words mentioned above and add their own words at the end. This memory exercise is one of the interesting games that help students to further strengthen their memory and repeat previous lessons. It should be said here that memory exercises include a lot of games. At the same time, these game, which is almost no different from the game we mentioned above, is a game of finding the last letter of the word. In this game, ten students are selected, and within the framework of the order, the next student must match the letter at the end of the word spoken by the previous student. This game also greatly contributes to increasing the potential and speed of intelligence of students.

DISCUSSION. Over the next ten years, it will be crucial for each state to prioritize teaching young people in areas that are in demand and have developed industries, while also increasing their literacy levels. These reforms are a bright proof of development in the education field of ESA countries, especially in attracting young people to learn foreign languages, modern technologies, and medical fields. This is a great achievement. At the same time, teaching difficult areas with easy game methods is considered one of the innovations.

CONCLUSION. As a conclusion, it should be noted that today, in order to provide easy and high-quality education for young people, these are among the projects, modern technologies and, of course, the games and methods discussed above. It is no exaggeration to say that it is one of our highest goals and obligations to bring up the young generation with knowledge, intelligence and education.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar;

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